

Design and Development of Hybrid Power source GO-KART

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Abstract

In this present work, a simulation-based investigation into the integration of hybrid power systems in go-kart vehicles carried out with a growing emphasis on sustainable transportation solutions, the implementation of hybrid power in recreational vehicles like go-karts holds significant potential. The simulation methodology involves modeling the performance characteristics of conventional go karts and integrating various hybrid power configurations to assess their impact on acceleration, top speed, and overall efficiency. Factors such as battery capacity, electric motor specifications, and regenerative braking systems are analyzed to optimize performance while maintaining the fun and excitement associated with go-karting. The results demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of hybrid power integration in go-karts, showcasing improvements in acceleration, reduced environmental impact, and enhanced overall performance. This project provides valuable insights for the design and development of eco-friendly recreational vehicles, aligning with the broader goal of promoting sustainability in the automotive industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

The general definition of any kart, a vehicle without suspension and differential. It is a vehicle specially designed for a flat track race. A wide range of engine karts were on track since the mid of the 20th century. The present automotive scenario motivates the eco-friendly vehicles to minimize the damage done by the harmful emissions done by the IC engines. As an alternative for the engine there is the electric motor which in comparison can give the same or even more power output. This can be implemented in the karting situation. Motor acts as a substitute for the engine and hence the go-kart gets drastically changed in both in its performance and design. The go-kart, thus runs only on electricity and is designed to meet the requirements for go-karting and also is being powered by the solar energy provided by the sun. The frame mostly acts as a suspension in go-karts. It must also possess sufficient strength not to break under extreme loading. So, flexibility should be compromised with more stiffness in the go-kart. The primary objective is to design a go-kart for the people. If we could drive a solar-powered car, that auto dream would come true.

The 3D view of the hybrid vehicle is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Hybrid Go-Kart

A solar panel is a packaged, connected assembly of solar cells, also called photovoltaic cells which are solid state devices that can convert solar energy directly into electrical energy through quantum mechanical transitions. They are noiseless and pollution-free with no rotating parts and need minimum maintenance. The electricity thus generated would then fuel the battery that would run the go-karts motors. Therefore, we would obtain an electrically driven go-kart that would travel on “free” energy with no harmful emissions, that can utilize its full power at all speeds, and would have very little maintenance cost. There is growing demand for fossil fuel like diesel and petrol to power the automotives and cater other needs of human.

2. LITERATURE

Mohammed Al-Garni et.al [1] The project encompasses material selection, design, and analysis with a focus on using 304 Stainless Steel and a 110cc engine. Various weight reduction techniques such as plywood molding and chassis optimization were explored. System testing involved impact tests on subsystems like the chassis, addressing challenges in fabrication and assembly, and reflecting on gained skills and contemporary issues like pollution and noise, with a conclusion emphasizing stability and lightweight design for future improvement. Shaik Himam Saheb et.al [2] Dives deep into creating a go-kart for a student competition, covering everything from design to engineering. They chose IS 1161 steel for the chassis because it's easy to work with and widely available, and they give specs for the chassis tubes. They used CAD and FEA to check the design's strength and displacement under different loads. There's a lot of detail on the chassis, wheelbase, steering, brakes, engine, and more. They did a ton of calculations on things like speed, torque, and stopping distance. The paper's backed up by references to books on vehicle dynamics and mechanics. The review says it's a solid overview of go-kart engineering, praising the detailed analysis and practical info it provides. Overall, it's a thorough guide for anyone building a go-kart, following standard engineering practices Naveen Kumar

et.al [3] The paper outlines the comprehensive engineering design process for an electric go-kart, covering frame construction, steering, brakes, transmission, and electrical components, with a focus on safety, ergonomics, performance, cost, and aesthetics. It utilizes finite element analysis (FEA) through ANSYS to assess frame durability and CAD tools like SolidWorks and Creo for 3D modeling and rendering, supported by detailed calculations for component selection. While praised for its thoroughness and methodical approach, suggestions for enhancing details on manufacturing and testing of the prototype are noted in the literature review. Sangeetha Krishnamoorthi et.al [4] The paper extensively explores the design and analysis of an electric go-kart, comparing chassis materials and ultimately selecting AISI 1018. Detailed specifications for various components and thorough analysis of stresses and deformations under different conditions are provided. While commended for its comprehensive overview and validation of the structural design, suggestions for further detailing on manufacturing and testing are offered in the literature review. Aashish Porwa et.al [5] The paper provides a comprehensive guide to designing and constructing an electric go-kart, emphasizing safety, strength, cost, weight reduction, and aesthetics. Key features include the selection of AISI 4130 steel for chassis, implementation of Ackermann steering geometry, and the use of hydraulic disc brakes for superior heat dissipation and braking performance. It aligns with EV technology trends by opting for brushless DC motors and lithium-ion batteries, while CAD and FEA simulations validate design choices, making it a valuable reference for electric go-kart and EV component design with potential for further improvements through final testing. Kiral Lal et.al [6] The paper applies engineering principles to determine key parameters like frame thickness and steering geometry, with FEA stress analysis validating structural integrity. While detailing component selections and fabrication, it lacks depth in areas such as engine performance, transmission design, manufacturing methods, and testing. Overall, it serves as a valuable reference for engineering students and motorsports enthusiasts, offering insights into go-kart design, though further exploration into manufacturing, testing, and comparative assessments is suggested for future improvement. A.Kuppuswamy et.al [7] The paper offers a comprehensive overview of designing an electric go-kart, emphasizing component selection and analysis using engineering principles. Clear explanations, block diagrams, and performance parameter calculations enhance understanding, with structural analysis validating the lightweight steel tube frame design. While lacking in comparative discussion on motor types and drivetrain configurations, additional details on testing procedures, results analysis, battery connections, and manufacturing methods could improve reproducibility and enhance the design. Sahadev Patade et.al [8] The paper provides a simplified guide to building an electric go-kart, emphasizing component selection and control with the support of mathematical calculations, diagrams, and simulations. While lacking details in areas like frame design, drivetrain, and safety considerations, it offers a solid foundation for

engineering students. Further steps include testing the prototype and suggesting refinements to enhance performance and functionality.

3. OBJECTIVES

- To design and Fabricate the Hybrid power source Go-Kart vehicle using Solar Power and Electric Motor.
- To create a prototype of Hybrid power source Go-Kart vehicle.

4. METHODOLOGY

The model was altered and retested for the ultimate design. The engineering and reverse engineering processes utilized during the iterative design phase of the vehicle vary depending on several factors, like the availability of parts and other concerns. The key design aims were to make the chassis lightweight while maintaining durability, to optimize the design by avoiding overdesigning, which would also help with cost savings, and we had a view of our kart with these in mind. To understand the design process better, we used a flow chart to plan the activities. This flow chart shown in figure 2 depicts the process of starting a project with an idea and completing it. The final front and side views of the hybrid vehicle are shown in figures 3 and 4.

Figure 2: Methodology of present work

Figure 3: Front View

Figure 4: Side View

4. CONCLUSION

Battery-powered and solar-powered go-karts represent innovative and sustainable alternatives to traditional gasoline-powered vehicles. With zero emissions and lower operating costs, they offer an environmentally friendly option for recreational and competitive racing. Additionally, the integration of solar panels further enhances their eco-friendliness and reduces dependency on grid electricity. Overall, these technologies showcase the potential for clean energy solutions in the realm of go-karting. Battery-powered and solar-powered go-karts not only offer eco-friendly alternatives but also pave the way for a more sustainable future in motorsports. Their silent operation and reduced environmental impact make them ideal for indoor tracks and sensitive outdoor environments. Moreover, their increasing popularity highlights a growing trend towards cleaner and more efficient

transportation solutions. As technology continues to advance, these vehicles are likely to become even more accessible, further promoting the adoption of renewable energy in the Auto mobile industry. In addition to their environmental benefits, battery-powered and solar-powered go-karts offer significant advantages in terms of maintenance and long-term cost savings. With fewer moving parts and simplified drivetrains, they require less upkeep compared to traditional gasoline engines, resulting in lower maintenance costs over time. Furthermore, their reliance on electricity, whether from batteries or solar panels, can lead to substantial savings on fuel expenses, making them economically attractive options for both individuals and businesses. As awareness of climate change and sustainability grow.

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